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IMMUNE ANEMIAS AND THROMBOCYTOPENIAS IN NON-HODGKIN'S LYMPHOMAS

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Abstract

Non-Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) are the most common hematological malignancies, the incidence of which has shown a significant increase in rates over the year, worldwide, as well as in the Republic of Moldova. [1] The association of immune complications in patients with NHL is common, which can be appreciated shortly before or during the manifestation of the malignant lymphoma. [2, 3] On the basis of a database of 64 NHLs patients registered at the Oncological Institute, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, a study was done to examine the clinical, and evolutionary particularities of immune anemias and thrombocytopenias in NHL. Immune hemolytic anemia (IHA) and immune thrombocytopenia (IT) are the most common immune complications and are more commonly in indolent NHL, advanced stages, nodal and spleen NHL onset, female gender. NHLs were most frequently associated with an immune comorbidity, and much less often concomitant immune comorbidities were appreciated.

Keywords: lymphoma, immune hemolytic anemia, immune thrombocytopenia.

Introduction

The association of immune complications in patients with NHL is common, which can be appreciated shortly before or during the manifestation of the malignant lymphoma. [2, 3] In some cases, the development of the immune component can be induced by the antineoplastic therapy. [4] It still remains an enigma the synthesis of antibodies after finishing the specific chemotherapy treatment applied to patients with NHL. [5] Based on the above, at the new patient with NHL can be not only the characteristic manifestations of NHL, but the association of immune hemolytic anemia manifested by anemic and hemolytic syndromes, immune thrombocytopenia represented by the hemorrhagic syndrome. Most immune comorbidities are associated with B-cell NHL, because B lymphocytes have a well-established role in the pathogenesis of immune disease, representing a source of erroneous synthesis of antibodies against one's own cells. [6, 7]

IHA is the most common immune complication recognized in patients with NHL, followed by Evans syndrome, erythroblastopenia, and IT. [8] Secondary IHA mainly develops against the background of lymphoproliferative diseases and autoimmune diseases, constituting approximately 50% of cases. [9] Hu et al's retrospective analysis of 4880 patients with NHL assessed IHA in 766 (15.7%) patients. In the case of patients with T-cell NHL, secondary IHA was appreciated in 57.14% of cases. [10]

Evans syndrome is more commonly diagnosed in patients aged 50-60 years, and in 27-50% of cases it is secondary to lymphoproliferative diseases and SLE. [11, 14] Hematological malignancies are the main factors with an impact on the development of Evans syndrome and its prognosis. [12, 13]

IT secondary to NHL, is a rare disease [15] and is diagnosed with a much lower frequency compared to IHA, being evaluated in only up to 1.8% of cases. [16, 17] The immune reaction underlying the development of secondary IT is complex, consisting of several consecutive stages in which B lymphocytes, T lymphocytes, NK, macrophages, cytokines participate.

Materials and methods

The study included 64 new patients with NHL, associated with immune comorbidities, treated in the Oncological Institute, Republic of Moldova, during the years 2020-2021. The average age of the patients is 62.3±3 years (33-76 years). The immune component developed more frequently in women - 44 (69%), compared to men - 20 (31%). The distribution of patients with NHL and autoimmune component according to the type of NHL demonstrated a more frequent association of immune disease in the case of the development of indolent NHL 34 (58%) patients as opposed to the development of aggressive NHL 30 (42%) patients. IHA and IT were confirmed by researching blood count, unconjugated bilirubin level, LDH, as well as response to immunosuppressive treatment. The database

of the selected material was processed statistically using Microsoft Excell, EpiInfo 7.2.2.6 and EpiMax Table programs.

Results

Immune complications were assessed more frequently in indolent NHL, as opposed to aggressive

NHL (58% versus 42%, respectively). IHA and IT represent the most frequent immune components (70.1%) associated with NHL patients, with an obvious predominance of IHA in 53.2% of cases, compared to IT in 16.9% of cases.

Pic. 1. Frequency distribution of immune comorbidities in patients with non-Hodgkin's lymphomas.

The distribution of patients with NHL according to the number of immune components associated with the malignant lymphoma, revealed an obvious predom-

inance of the association of a single immune component – 53 (82.8%) cases and only 11 (17.2%) patients were diagnosed with associations of 2 or 3 concomitant immune complications.

Pic. 2. Types of associations of the immune component in patients with non-Hodgkin's lymphomas.

Independent of the type of NHL, indolent or aggressive, IHA (31.1% and 22%, respectively) and IT (12.9% and 3.8%, respectively) prevailed. We observe a higher frequency of development of immune complications in indolent NHL.

IHA and IT were appreciated in both genders. IHA was diagnosed in 35% of cases in female patients with NHL, which represents a higher frequency than the association of IHA in male patients with NHL - 18.1% cases. The same fact was also appreciated in the case of IT, which appeared more frequently (11.6%) in women with NHL than in men, in whom the same autoimmune complication was diagnosed in only 5.2% of cases.

The immune component was appreciated in the case of NHL with nodal 33 (51.6%) and extranodal 31 (48.4%) onset. The analysis of the frequency distribution of the association of the type of immune component in patients with NHL according to the location of the primary tumor focus shows an obvious discrepancy.

Multiple associations of immune components have been evaluated in the case of nodal onset of malignant lymphoma, especially in the peripheral lymph nodes, followed by spleen onset. The most frequent IHA was appreciated in the case of the onset of the disease at the spleen-25.9% cases, then at the peripheral lymph nodes 14.2% cases, abdominal lymph nodes in 6.5%, mediastinal lymph nodes 3.8% and very rarely in only 1 (1.3%) IHA developed at the onset of the lymphoma in the soft tissues and stomach. IT was evaluated in patients with NHL whose primary tumor focus developed in the spleen 8 (10.3%), peripheral lymph nodes 4 (5.1%) and abdominal lymph nodes 1 (1.3%).

In advanced stages (III and IV) of NHL, immune complications predominated, being evaluated in 71 (92.2%) patients. In stages I and II, where the same immune complications were present only in 6 (7.8%) patients. IHA and IT developed most frequently in advanced NHL (51.9% and 16.8%, respectively).

We estimated that in 67.5% of cases immune complications developed during NHL. According to the medical history of patients with NHL, prior to the diagnosis of malignant lymphoma, the immune component was present only in 25 (32.5%) patients. Simultaneously with NHL, only 3 types of immune components were evaluated: IHA - 40 (51.9%) patients, IT in 11 (14.2%) patients and in 1 (1.3%) case of autoimmune thyroiditis.

Conclusion

IHA and IT are the most common immune complications and are more commonly associated in patients with indolent, generalized, nodal and spleen NHL onset, female gender. The distribution of patients with NHL according to the number of immune components associated with the malignant lymphoma, revealed an obvious predominance of the association of a single immune component.

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